

**A STUDY ON OPPORTUNITIES, PROBLEMS & PERCEPTIONS OF
RETAIL INVESTORS CONCERNING MUTUAL FUNDS**

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Abstract: The Indian mutual fund industry has emerged as a significant financial intermediary, contributing to capital market stability, wealth creation, and financial inclusion. Established under the Indian Trusts Act 1882, and regulated by SEBI, mutual funds have witnessed exponential growth with Assets Under Management (AUM) rising from ₹5.89 lakh crore in 2008 to ₹65.74 lakh crore in 2025. This paper examines the evolution, classification, and role of mutual funds in India. It highlights the factors that influence investor perceptions, opportunities, and challenges. Literature suggests that investment decisions are shaped by past performance, risk tolerance, financial literacy, regulatory frameworks, and brand reputation. Opportunities such as diversification, professional management, liquidity, tax benefits and digital innovations have increased retail investor participation. With SIP adoption and equity-oriented schemes leading growth. However, issues including regulatory changes, market risks, and heavy dependence on fund managers remain persistent challenges. Findings reveal a structural shift in Indian household savings toward market-based instruments with equity and passive funds driving industry expansion. The study underscores the need for enhanced financial literacy, transparent disclosures and investor education to balance risk and return effectively. It concludes that mutual funds, supported by digitalisation and evolving regulatory frameworks and will continue to play a pivotal role in shaping India's investment landscape.

Keywords: Awareness, Mutual funds, Perception, Investor behaviour.

INTRODUCTION:

Mutual Funds in India are established in the form of a Trust under the Indian Trusts Act, 1882, as per the SEBI (Mutual Funds) Regulations, 1996. Mutual funds have emerged as vital instruments for mobilising both institutional and individual savings. Over the past few decades, the mutual fund industry has experienced remarkable growth and has become a significant force in the Indian capital market. Remarkably, the industry's Assets Under Management (AUM) has tripled in just five years, increasing from Rs. 24.55 trillion as of May 31, 2020, to Rs. 72.20 trillion as of May 31, 2025. (1) Compound interest is a well-established method through which mutual fund investments generate returns. Moreover, the participation of women in the financial sector has increased significantly. The rising number of women opting to open demat accounts reflects this positive trend, which bodes well for overall economic growth. (2).

Indian mutual funds are powerful financial intermediaries that play a crucial role in stabilising the monetary system and enhancing capital allocation efficiency. Mutual funds provide a range of

schemes to fulfil investors' growing needs. **(Bharti Gaggar, 2021)**. An investor's income has a significant impact on their investment objectives. While government securities are considered risk-free, they often fail to appeal to those seeking above-average returns. Their main advantage is stability, offering certainty and low volatility. 29.4% of basic investors rank government securities in the 5th position, and another 29.4% place them in the 6th. This reflects a moderate preference for these securities, with return being a key driver in their investment decisions. **(Walia & Kiran, 2009)**. Mutual funds play a vital role in enhancing every business activity, serving as a cornerstone for growth and opportunity. **(Hameed, 2017)**. Effective risk management is critical for success. **(Muhammad Imran, 2017)**. The mutual fund industry has experienced remarkable growth, with assets under management (AUM) increasing from Rs. 5.89 lakh crore in May 2008 to Rs. 65.74 lakh crore in March 2025, a ninefold rise in less than two decades. The growth is driven by rising retail participation, digital adoption, increasing financial awareness, higher disposable incomes, and regulatory changes that foster competition, among other factors **(AMFI REPORT 2025)**. (3).

It is crucial to explore the factors influencing investors. Investigating the key aspects valued in mutual funds helps us understand what drives their investment decisions. Additionally, recognising the flow of mutual funds is essential for success in this field. **(Parida & Wang, 2018)**. It is necessary to examine various factors influencing investment. The Indian financial market is experiencing impressive growth, offering a diverse range of financial products to investors. A standout innovation that has significantly empowered small investors to build wealth is the concept and design of mutual funds. This trend is unmistakable, as investors in India increasingly recognise the advantages of mutual funds in their investment strategies. **(Kulkarni Medha Harshad, 2019)**. Most mutual fund investors distribute their savings across various well-managed mutual fund schemes, in the hope of beating the market through a combination of fundamental and technical analysis **(Babbar, 2016)**.

One of the basic strategies for generating profits is to buy low and sell high. However, in today's dynamic investment landscape, it is increasingly evident that accepting higher risks can lead to more substantial returns. As such, investors must navigate the complexities of financial markets by carefully balancing risk and reward. This evolving scenario underscores the importance of making informed decisions and adopting a strategic approach to investing. In recent years, several funds have displayed exceptional performance, yielding higher returns for their investors. Most investors developing their tax strategy for surplus funds support increasing the tax exemption limit under Section 80C. **(Harwani, Gurmukh, Hitesh, 2021)**.

In making investment decisions, investors are more cautious about achieving higher returns with minimal risk. Still, it is not possible to get abnormal returns when the markets are efficient. Literature suggests that individual investors generally do not consider mutual funds to be a hazardous investment; however, when compared with other financial avenues, the market appears more attractive. Those investors who do not want to take the complete risk of capital market volatility invest in mutual funds, relying on the professional financial manager of the funds. A small number of investors consider mutual funds to be the most preferred investment, ranking them in first position **(Walia & Kiran, 2009)**. Mutual funds mitigate investment risk by diversifying their holdings across multiple companies within various industries and sectors. Therefore, if one invests in a single company, it tends to be a higher-risk investment compared to investing in mutual funds (Rai University, 2012). Another study finds a significant relationship between the income level of investors and their perception of investment returns from mutual fund investments. In other words, when an investor's income level is low, they will invest in mutual funds for secure returns. However, when they have a high income, the investor will move to a financial institution to obtain higher returns, albeit at a higher risk **(Maheen M., 2022)**.

Classification of Mutual Funds:

The Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) has introduced guidelines for categorising mutual funds into five broad categories. These categories are based on the risk and return of the investment and are designed to make mutual fund investments simple, transparent and comparable.

SEBI's five broad mutual fund categories are:

1. Equity-oriented schemes.
2. Debt-oriented schemes
3. Hybrid schemes
4. Solution-oriented schemes
5. Others

Equity Funds: Equity funds mainly invest in stocks, providing the highest growth potential. These funds are ideal for investors with a high-risk tolerance seeking long-term capital appreciation.

Subcategories:

1. Large-Cap Funds: Large-cap mutual funds are equity funds that primarily invest in the stocks of the 100 largest companies in India, based on market capitalisation. These companies are among the most well-known brands in the country, and many Indians use their products daily.

2. Mid-Cap Funds: Mid-cap mutual funds are equity funds that invest in the stocks of mid-sized companies in India, based on their market capitalisation. These companies are among the fastest-growing in the country and are currently at a stage similar to where today's industry leaders were just a few years ago.

3. Small-Cap Funds: Small-cap funds are equity funds that focus on investing in the stocks of small companies in India, specifically those with a market capitalisation of less than Rs. 5,000 crores. These companies rank among the top 250 in the country but are often not well-known in everyday life. While small-cap companies have the potential to generate impressive returns, they are also highly volatile, which can lead to short- to medium-term losses.

4. Sectoral Funds: Investors should concentrate on specific sectors like technology, healthcare, or consumer goods, enabling them to strategically target and capitalise on growth opportunities in these dynamic areas.

Debt Funds: These funds specialise in investing in fixed-income securities, such as bonds and government obligations, designed for conservative investors who prioritise stability in their portfolios. By focusing on these low-risk investments, these funds aim to provide reliable and consistent returns, allowing investors to blend safety with growth potential. This investment approach appeals to those seeking to preserve capital while generating a steady income stream.

Subcategories:

1. Liquid funds: Liquid funds primarily invest in debt instruments with maturities not exceeding 91 days, rendering them almost risk-free. They seldom experience negative returns. Compared to savings bank accounts, liquid funds offer equivalent liquidity with higher yields. Numerous mutual fund companies provide instant redemption for liquid fund investments through specialised debit cards.

2. Short-Term Funds: These debt funds invest in instruments with maturities ranging from one to three years. Short-term funds are suitable for conservative investors, as they are not significantly

affected by interest rate movements.

3. Gilt Funds: Gilt funds exclusively invest in highly-rated government securities with minimal credit risk. Since governments rarely default on the loans they issue as debt instruments, gilt funds represent an ideal option for risk-averse investors seeking fixed income.

Hybrid Funds: These funds combine both equity and debt investments, providing a balanced approach to risk and return. They are ideal for investors seeking moderate risk with potential growth and stability.

Subcategories:

1. Conservative Hybrid Funds. The Conservative Hybrid Fund mandates an allocation of 10% to 25% of total assets in Equity and Equity-related financial instruments, while the remaining 75% to 90% should be allocated to Debt instruments. The Debt asset class includes fixed-income-generating securities such as treasury bills, corporate bonds, commercial papers, certificates of deposit, and other similar instruments.

2. Balanced Hybrid Funds: This Mutual Fund scheme allocates a minimum of 40% and a maximum of 60% to both Equity and Debt asset classes. For investors seeking long-term capital growth, a balanced Hybrid Fund can be an appealing option, as the inclusion of Debt instruments helps mitigate the risks associated with the Equity component.

3. Aggressive Hybrid Funds: Under this scheme, investors are permitted to allocate a minimum of 65% and a maximum of 80% to the Equity asset class. Meanwhile, the allocation to Debt securities can range from 20% to 35%. This structure offers the potential for higher returns with reduced risk, thanks to the inclusion of Debt Securities in the portfolio.

Solution-oriented: Solution-oriented mutual funds are designed to help investors achieve specific financial goals, such as retirement or a child's education, by offering a customised investment approach. These funds typically have a lock-in period, encouraging long-term investment for goals that may take years to reach.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

1)– Maheen M. [2022] –Study shows that different versions of alternative risk-adjusted models (conditional and unconditional versions) indicate the presence of superior performance in the Indian MF industry. The cross-sectional average suggests that the exceptional performance is not significant.

2)–Shreekant, Gaurav [2021]—This study compares the performances of the different categories of equity funds, viz., large-cap (actively managed) funds, significant and mid-cap funds, Mid-Cap funds, Small-Cap funds, multi-cap funds, and ELSS funds, over the period April 2007—March 2019, using different risk-return measures.

3) Harwani, Gurmukh Hitesh [2021] - The findings of this research pertain to the occupation of ELSS mutual fund investors in the Indian scenario. The highest number of investors for this scheme is salaried individuals, which accounts for half of the total respondents among ELSS investors. The reason for this is that they are well-educated and have knowledge of these products from friends and relatives in the market. Most investors planning their tax strategy for surplus funds are in favour of increasing the tax exemption limit under Section 80C.

4) Bharti Gaggar [2021]—The study reveals that Indian mutual funds are powerful financial intermediaries that play a crucial role in stabilising the economic system and enhancing capital allocation efficiency. Mutual funds provide a range of schemes to fulfil investors' growing needs.

5) Maheshwari [2020] – The study shows that, in India, the capital market suffers from a lack of diverse venture options, as opposed to customers, to help them invest in various risk devices and ensure profitable returns. Mutual funds offer financial practitioners the highest return and the least risk. In the Indian capital markets, enhancing various investment fund schemes has been one of the most effective risk management routes for developing noteworthy investments. The results of this analysis will help investors make informed decisions about future investments.

6) Tripathi & Japee [2020] – This study demonstrates that the Indian stock market offers investors multiple investment avenues, enabling them to diversify across various sectors and achieve profitable returns. Open-end funds are one of the key instruments for generating significant investment growth within a stock market. The results of this report will provide investors with a thorough basis for making informed future investment choices.

7) Kulkarni Medha Harshad [2019] - The findings of this research indicate that the Indian Financial market is growing at a good pace, with various financial products being offered in the market. One of the financial innovations that has significantly helped small investors accumulate wealth is the concept and design of mutual funds. It is better experienced by the Indian financial market and the growing inclination of investors towards mutual funds.

8)—Makwana, Kiritkumar Revabhai [2018] - **The findings suggest that social media plays no role in increasing the number of clients of mutual fund agents.** Therefore, adapting social media platforms to market mutual funds is not a good idea for asset management companies. The results also indicate that digitisation has a minimal impact on the increasing number of clients for mutual fund agents. The results conclude that the Longevity of mutual fund agents is not related to the training programs conducted by asset management companies.

9)-Trivedi, Rajesh [2018] – It is found that the investment of respondents begins before they reach the age of 30 years, increasing as they approach middle age. Investors aged 41-50 contribute more than those aged 51-60. This shows that the middle-aged category investors have a risk-appetite nature. The least investment comes from the age group of older and retired people, as they are low-risk takers and need a fixed and secure income at this stage of life. It is observed that the coverage of higher education is higher than that of the primary level among the respondents, which implies that education can boost mutual fund investment.

10)- O.V.A.M. Sridevi [2018] – Results of the study have shown that out of the two schemes, both mid-cap and small-cap funds, have evidence of outperforming the benchmark return. Not all the funds have represented positive values. In the mid-cap fund, the performance of the Axis Balanced Fund is insignificant, whereas in the small-cap fund, the performance of the HSBC Balanced Fund is considered desirable. However, based on the above study, it can be observed that the schemes yield diverse results.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To determine the elements influencing people's perceptions of mutual fund investing.
2. To determine the elements influencing people's problems and opportunities in mutual funds.

RESEARCH GAP:

1. The current growth of investors and their impact on the market is unclear due to insufficient information.
2. Moreover, the limited literature addressing investors' challenges, opportunities, and perceptions signifies a critical gap in our understanding of the investment landscape. Essential aspects, such as common mistakes during market entry and exit, as well as trends that could significantly influence

the market's trajectory, appear to be underrepresented in existing research.

3. There is a lack of research on market trends that could help new investors better understand market fluctuations.

HYPOTHESIS:

H_{a1}: There is a significant relationship between the period and MF profit

H_{a2}: There is a significant relationship between risk and return when investing in mutual funds.

DISCUSSION:

(A) To determine the elements influencing people's perceptions of mutual fund investing:

1. Past Performance: Historical returns and consistent performance not only reflect a fund's track record but also instil confidence among investors, shaping their perceptions and expectations for future growth.

2. Risk Tolerance: Understanding one's risk appetite is crucial; investors who acknowledge their risk tolerance and the inherent risks associated with mutual funds are better equipped to make informed investment decisions that align with their financial goals.

3. Financial Literacy: A solid grasp of financial markets, investment instruments, and key concepts empowers investors to navigate the complexities of mutual funds, thereby enhancing their ability to evaluate options and make informed, strategic choices. **(Chakrabarti et)**

4. Brand Reputation: The credibility and reputation of a fund house or asset management company play a pivotal role in investor trust; a strong brand often signifies reliability, professionalism, and a commitment to the interests of investors.

5. Regulatory Environment: Staying informed about changes in regulations and investor protection measures is essential; these changes can impact fund operations and investor rights, influencing how investors perceive the safety and integrity of their investments.

6. Economic Conditions: Fluctuations in market trends, interest rates, and broader economic conditions serve as critical external factors that influence investor sentiment, often dictating the opportunities and challenges that investors face.

7. Transparency and Disclosure: Prioritising clarity and transparency in fund operations, including comprehensive reporting of holdings and performance, is essential. This openness fosters trust, enabling investors to make well-informed decisions based on accurate information. Essential.

8. Customer Support: The quality of customer service, responsiveness, and support has a significant influence on investor satisfaction and perception.

9. Investor Education: By providing clear education on mutual funds, we can enhance investors' understanding of their benefits, such as diversification and professional management, while also addressing inherent risks like market volatility and fees. This balanced approach empowers investors to make informed decisions that align with their financial goals.

(B) To determine the elements influencing people's opportunities and problems in mutual funds: -

Opportunities In Mutual Funds:

1. Diversification: Mutual funds enable investors to create a diversified portfolio, significantly reducing the risk associated with individual investments.

2. **Professional Management:** With the expertise of skilled fund managers, investors can harness the potential for enhanced returns through informed security selection and management.
3. **Liquidity:** The flexibility of open-ended mutual funds offers seamless entry and exit, creating an investment journey that adapts to your needs.
4. **Tax Benefits:** Exploring mutual funds, such as Equity Linked Savings Schemes (ELSS), unlocks valuable tax advantages under Section 80C of the Income Tax Act, paving the way for smarter financial decisions for ELSS mutual fund investors in the Indian scenario. The highest number of investors for this scheme is salaried individuals, which accounts for half of the total respondents among ELSS investors. The reason for this is that they are well-educated and have knowledge of these products from friends and relatives in the market. Most investors planning their tax strategy for surplus funds are in favour of increasing the tax exemption limit under Section 80C. (Harwani, GurmukhHitesh 2021)
5. **Systematic Investment Plans (SIPs):** SIPs encourage investors to make consistent, small contributions, making the path to wealth-building an effortless and rewarding experience.
6. **Technological Advancements:** Thanks to digital platforms, investing in mutual funds has become not just effortless but also a remarkable opportunity for anyone ready to take control of their financial future.

Share of retail investors on the rise:

Upon analysing the investor type AUM breakdown, it was observed that the share of retail investors in the total AUM mix had increased over the past five years, from 19.8% in March 2019 to 27.9% in March 2024. This growth highlights the increasing awareness and accessibility of mutual fund investments, driven by enhanced financial literacy, awareness campaigns such as "Mutual Funds Sahi Hai," and the expansion of financial inclusion in over 30 cities. This, in turn, is augmenting the adoption of SIPs, owing to their affordability, disciplined approach, and growing accessibility through fintech platforms and robo-advisors. The corporate share in AUM dropped from 38.6% in March 2019 to 35.5% in March 2024, a decline of 3.1%. Corporate investors dominate the debt mutual fund segment, accounting for more than 60% of the total debt AUM. Within corporate investments, a significant portion—more than two-thirds—is allocated to short-maturity debt categories, including overnight funds, liquid funds, ultra-short-duration funds, low-duration funds, and money market funds. Among these, corporate investors contribute more than 80% of the AUM in overnight funds and over 75% of the AUM in liquid funds, primarily for temporary parking of surplus funds.

Source: AMFI, Crisil Intelligence

Problems Faced by Retail Investors in Mutual Funds:

1. Regulatory Changes: Frequent changes in government policies and regulations set forth by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) can create a significant degree of uncertainty in the financial market. These alterations can impact investor confidence, influence market stability, and affect the overall business environment. As companies and investors strive to adapt to new guidelines and compliance requirements, the resulting unpredictability can hinder strategic planning and long-term investment decisions, ultimately shaping market dynamics and performance.

2. Everything is in the hands of the fund manager: In a mutual fund, the fund manager has substantial control over investment decisions. This creates a problem for the investor, as the entire control over their money rests in the hands of the manager.

3. Market risk: Retail investors often do not understand that mutual fund investments, especially those in equity and hybrid funds, are subject to market fluctuations. When the market falls, they may panic and withdraw money at a loss, rather than staying invested for long-term growth.

FINDINGS:

In the remarkable journey of the Indian mutual fund industry, it is evident that we have made significant strides in achieving our goals. The industry's assets under management (AUM) have grown from Rs. 5.89 lakh crore in May 2008 to Rs. 65.74 lakh crore in March 2025, an eleven-fold rise in less than two decades. This growth underscores the industry's pivotal role in empowering Indian households and investors, offering a robust platform for wealth creation and financial inclusion. Notably, the share of mutual funds in Indian household savings has risen from 7.6% in FY21 to 8.4% in FY23, reflecting increasing investor confidence. To see this impressive increase, the investor starts investing in mutual funds. The equity category led the growth, with its AUM (assets under management) share surging from 29.4% in March 2019 to 44.0% in March 2024, demonstrating a preference for equities among investors.

Equity AUM grew 2.35 times in five years from Rs. 7.00 lakh crore in March 2019 to Rs. 23.49 lakh crore in March 2024, driven by substantial inflows and market-to-market gains (MTM). AUM across all equity categories experienced more than 100% growth during this period, as this era encouraged people to invest in mutual funds.

Debt AUM increased from Rs. 9.64 lakh crore to Rs. 12.62 lakh crore, showcasing a steady growth in fixed-income investments; however, its overall share in AUM saw a significant decline due to reduced investor flows. Hybrid schemes AUM doubled from Rs. 3.36 lakh crore to Rs. 7.22 lakh crore, reflecting the growing investor appetite for diversified investment solutions.

The passive category saw the highest growth, with its AUM rising over five times, from 6.1% of total industry AUM in 2019 to 17.0% in 2024, reaching Rs. 9.09 lakh crore. This rapid expansion highlights the increasing demand for low-cost investment options, including index funds and exchange-traded funds (ETFs). However, the share remains very low when compared with developed economies like the US, where the share of passive funds' AUM stood at approximately 51% as of December 2024.

Category-wise industry AUM break up (in %)

Source: AMFI, Crisil Intelligence
Others includes closed-ended funds, solution-oriented funds and fund of funds

CONCLUSION:

Over the last three decades, it has been noticed that people saved their money at home. They bought gold/ bonds, and invested their money in real estate. However, this concept has changed, and most people now invest their money in the market through mutual funds. There are fund managers who have been playing a very significant role in investing. In this digital era, everything is transparent. We all know that which fund or stock in which fund manager has invested money.

There were many problems associated with investing in mutual funds, but the digital era has made everything accessible on the internet. Now the people are aware about the savings and they are learning how to manage their risk efficiently. Because risk is the basis characteristic of the market.

Category-wise industry AUM break up (in %)

Source: AMFI, Crisil Intelligence
Others includes closed-ended funds, solution-oriented funds and fund of funds

This is the era of investment, as the **Investopedia reports** the return on gold is less than the market return. As we are aware of the history of returns, we find that the return on gold is 9.47% while the market typically offers a return of at least 11.2%. Additionally, we can withdraw money from it as needed. In present time, even a middle-class person is becoming more conscious about their future. Therefore, the investor's perception changes. They start investing in the mutual funds. Currently, investing money in the market has become relatively easy. We can invest money in a simple way, either weekly or monthly or depending on the availability of funds.

Currently, **AMFI reports** show that around ₹ 28,464 crore invested in a mutual fund as SIP monthly (July 2025), which is an increase from ₹ 27,269 crore (June 2025). The mutual fund industry has experienced remarkable growth, with assets under management (AUM) increasing from Rs 5.89 lakh crore in May 2008 to Rs 65.74 lakh crore in March 2025. An elevenfold rise in less than two decades. The growth is driven by rising retail participation, digital adoption, increasing financial awareness, higher disposable incomes, and regulatory changes that foster competition among other factors.

It was observed that the share of retail investors in the total AUM mix had increased over the past five years, from 19.8% in March 2019 to 27.9% in March 2024. This growth highlights the increasing awareness and accessibility of mutual fund investments

The Indian economy is the fourth-largest economy in the world. In the future, it is expected to grow further. Sectors like power and infrastructure present the best investment opportunities. This study highlights several factors (Tax Benefits, Systematic Investment Plans, Liquidity, etc) that motivate individuals to invest in mutual funds. As a developing country, India is progressing steadily, presenting various growth opportunities. By investing in mutual funds, there is potential to substantially increase our income, possibly doubling, tripling, or even quadrupling it.

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